

The Influence of Content Marketing towards Word of Mouth with a Mediating Role of Brand Awareness: Study Case at Lazada Indonesia

Silvi Dwi Oktaviani¹, Harimukti Wandebori²

^{1,2} Magister Business Administration, Institut Teknologi Bandung, Jl. Ganesha no. 10, Bandung 40132, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The significant decrease in the number of visitors and not the first rank e-commerce platform in Indonesia indicates a decline in brand awareness and positive word-of-mouth. Considering the current critical condition of Lazada Indonesia in terms of awareness, the company must implement an innovative strategy to maintain the attraction of the platform and social media, while also gaining new customers and retaining existing ones. One approach is to efficiently utilize and enhance content marketing using social media to increase awareness of the company, which could result in increased positive word of mouth.

The purpose of this study is to explore the influence of content marketing has on word of mouth among users of Lazada Indonesia, while also examining the mediating role of brand awareness. The data for this research were obtained from a sample of 85 respondents who are users of Lazada Indonesia and who follow Lazada Indonesia's social media accounts. The analysis and verification of all the results were conducted using SEM-PLS.

The research findings show that Lazada Indonesia's content marketing has a positive influence on word of mouth and brand awareness among its users. The influence of brand awareness on word of mouth is positive but low influence. Furthermore, content marketing has a positive influence on word of mouth through brand awareness a mediating variable.

Research findings indicated that Lazada Indonesia's content marketing has a positive also significant influence on word of mouth and brand awareness among Lazada Indonesia's users. Same as the result of brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on word of mouth. Moreover, there is a positive and significant influence of content marketing on word of mouth through brand awareness as a mediating variable.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Content Marketing, E-commerce, Word of Mouth.

INTRODUCTION

Internet users have grown tremendously in recent years. In 2022-2023, the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association published data, that in a population of 275.773.901 people, 215.626.156 people are internet users, which means the internet penetration rate in Indonesia already reach 78.19% by 2023. According to data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association for the time frame 2023, there are 5 primary reasons why people in Indonesia are using the internet, as well as for using social media, accessing news or information, for work or school, accessing public service, and for online or mobile transaction. Transactions conducted online have developed into an essential component of our routine. Our shopping, bill-paying, and financial management have all been changed as a result of these virtual transfers of price, which have provided us with an unprecedented level of convenience and effectiveness. Online shopping is one of the businesses that leverage digital platforms. The popularity of online shopping has risen because of the convenience and simplicity of online purchasing. Particularly during the COVID-19 outbreak. COVID-19 has turned into a pandemic and spread to several countries worldwide (WHO, 2020). Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, customers all over the world are staying indoors and spending more time online than ever before, searching for goods and services that they usually purchase in stores. As a result, the potential market has shifted to the digital.

According to a McKinsey report, Indonesia's e-commerce sector will accrue up to eightfold from 2017 to 2022. By 2022, online commerce sales are expected to exceed \$65 billion. In addition to generating revenue, they believe that online commerce may unlock broad societal influence. The increasing number of expanding businesses creates intensified rivalry, thus motivating companies to showcase improved benefits and capabilities to compete in the industry using various existing marketing strategies.

Content marketing is merely one of numerous digital marketing strategies and tactics that entrepreneurs could use. In the technological era, content has emerged as the most critical element in the creation of online media. The adage "Content is King" underscores the significance of creating top-notch content that contributes to the advancement of consumer understanding.

According to a recent study by Siege Media, stated that 54.5 percent of businesses plan on raising their content marketing expenditures in 2024 compared to 2023. This demonstrates the significance of content; content marketing is the newest trend in the marketing industry nowadays, and it is extensively used to increase revenue for businesses.

Content marketing is an effective strategy for promoting products and establishing strong connections with consumers. This marketing strategy enables firms to effectively engage with their intended audiences and discern their challenges. Businesses have the ability to easily create content that tackles these concerns, and they employ content marketing to sway their intended audience and craft an immersive encounter for them. Despite intense competition, it is crucial for content creators to prioritize the creation and release of high-quality content rather than focusing on quantity.

Utilizing content marketing is a highly effective strategy to encourage brand awareness and word of mouth. Companies must understand the importance of effectively managing their marketing efforts on social media platforms by utilizing valuable content marketing. This strategy is crucial for enhancing brand awareness also promoting favorable word of mouth. Therefore, concerning the phenomenon described above, the reason for conducting this research is to ascertain the influence of content marketing on brand awareness and word of mouth.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. Content Marketing

In the context of marketing, as stated by (Pulizzi & Barret, 2009), content marketing refers to an approach that involves the creation and dissemination of material that is significant, important, and pertinent. The goal of this approach is to attract, acquire, and engage a particular target audience in order to drive profitable customer behavior. There is a difference between just licensing media and content marketing, which entails the ownership of the material. It is a form of marketing that is focused at acquiring new customers and keeping the customer that company already have (Andaç et al., 2016). According to (Pulizzi, 2012), content marketing is a strategic process that involves marketing content that is relevant and valuable in order to attract, acquire, and engage a specific target audience. The fundamental purpose of content marketing is to generate lucrative customer behavior.

Content marketing defines a systematic approach to creating high-quality, significant, unique, valuable, educational, appealing, more frequently changing, and more applicable data than that of rivals, presented in various formats to attract and retain customers (Handley & Chapman, 2011). Companies and brands have used content marketing in many formats. According to (Geneulis, 2011), content marketing refers to the strategy of promoting such a brand or business by making and sharing valuable text, video, or audio content through various channels, both online and offline, with both direct and indirect methods. The content may take several forms, Examples of different forms of content include long form pieces such as essays, blogs and electronic books, a brief form material like Twitter updates, Facebook updates, and images, as well as conversational-form content such as sharing content on social media or engaging in discussions in comments or online forums.

The objectives of content marketing vary across different stages of the consumer journey. Content Marketing is a strategic approach aimed at attracting a fresh audience in order to gain deeper insights into the company's activities. Once the audience has identified the company's business, the primary objective of content marketing is to persuade and retain the audience as clients who are loyal to the company's products or services. In addition, content marketing can be utilized to enhance brand recognition, attract potential customers, cultivate consumer loyalty, and expand the size of an audience (Odden, 2012). Content marketing can utilize indirect methods of persuasion to attract customers to a particular product. Additionally, it can incite curiosity and captivate the audience, leading to a boost in sales and fostering customer loyalty (Ajina, 2019).

Types of Content Marketing:

1. Entertain: Designed to entertain clients and engage with customers through various means such as interactive games, quizzes, memes, competitions, and videos.
2. Inspire: Inspiration-driven content has the ability to motivate customers
3. Educate: Education content refers to content that is designed to provide customers with knowledge and information about a particular product or service.
4. Convince: Convince content refers to persuasive content that aims to persuade the audience.

Dimension of Content Marketing:

This study utilizes the degree or level established by (Andaç et al., 2016), who developed five dimensions to characterize and categorize content marketing. The five-dimensional levels are:

1. Shareable: The company's content marketing should be easily shareable by the audience and evoke emotional reactions, thereby stimulating the audience's desire to suggest the content and establish connections with people who share their interests.
2. Easy to Understand: Content marketing entails conveying messages and information to the audience, making it essential for content to be clear and easily comprehensible to the audience.
3. Incentive: Content marketing should encourage clients to engage in a specific action
4. Easily Accessible: content marketing should be easily accessible to everyone through social media platforms.
5. Absorbing: Content marketing should effectively engage customers by catching their attention and providing them with valuable information

B. Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is an indicator of how well consumers are able to recognize, accept, and recall a certain brand in any circumstance (Percy & Rossiter, 1992). In accordance with (Aaker, 1991), the term "brand awareness" refers to the capacity of a prospective purchaser to recognize or recall a certain brand as being associated with a particular product category. According to (Keller, 2009) brand awareness is all about the influence and influence a brand has on consumers' memories, allowing them to easily recall or recognize the brand in various situations. Having a strong brand awareness can significantly decrease the amount of time and uncertainty that consumers face when trying to find a product to purchase. Consumers are expected to make their brand choices based on the information they have. According to Aaker (Aaker, 1996), brand awareness can be measured through 4 levels: brand recognition, brand recall, top-of-the-mind brand, and dominant brand. Understanding the concept of brand recognition and brand recall is crucial in the world of marketing. Brand recognition refers to how familiar consumers are with a particular brand, while brand recall is the ability to think of a specific brand when presented with a range of products (Farjam & Hongyi, 2015). Being a brand that immediately comes to mind means being the most recognized brand in its product classification. According to (Aaker, 1996), the brand dominance level is determined by how much the brand replaces the product category.

C. Word-of-Mouth

Word of mouth abbreviated as WOM is the informal interchange of advice and recommendations between customers. Typically, it is participatory, fast, and free from commercial bias. Word-of-mouth has a large influence on customer behavior. Word-of-mouth (WOM) can have a favorable influence on brand choice, known as positive word-of-mouth (PWOM), or a negative one, known as negative word-of-mouth (NWOM) (East et al., 2008).

Positive word-of-mouth (WOM) refers to a customer's expectation that they will discuss an occurrence with at least one person who does not have a direct involvement in the connection with the service (Swanson & Charlene Davis, 2003). According to (East et al., 2008), positive word-of-mouth (WOM) can influence consumers to choose a certain brand. Moreover, it is widely acknowledged that satisfaction has the potential to generate positive word-of-mouth ((Pang, 2021).

Social media platforms serve as a prime illustration of *electronic* word of mouth. Word of mouth is an influential marketing instrument. AT&T discovered that it was one of the most efficient catalysts for its sales, in addition to unaided advertising awareness. The dissemination of information by individuals has been the primary means by which certain businesses have been founded, as opposed to the more conventional methods of promotion. Word-of-mouth marketing aims to actively involve customers in promoting products, services, and brands by encouraging them to speak favorably about them to others. Viral marketing incentivizes individuals to share and disseminate online content about a particular product or service.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure I. Conceptual Framework

The following hypothesis for this research:

- H1. Content Marketing has a positive influence on Brand Awareness at Lazada Indonesia.
- H2. Content Marketing has a positive influence on Word of Mouth at Lazada Indonesia.
- H3. Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Word of Mouth at Lazada Indonesia.
- H4. Content Marketing has a position influence on Word of Mouth through Brand Awareness at Lazada Indonesia.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a quantitative research technique, focusing on the population of e-commerce users, especially Lazada Indonesia users and those who are followers of Lazada on social media. The sample was chosen using purposive sampling, employing precise criteria that targeted individuals who actively engage and read Lazada Indonesia's social media content, as well as being active users of the Lazada platform. In consideration of the sample size estimates conducted by (Hair et al., 2019), the required number of samples should be five times the number of indicators included in the study. Utilizing the operationalization or indicators of variables as previously outlined, this study utilized 17 indicators, leading to a sample size of 85 respondents. Furthermore, data analysis encompassed descriptive statistical analysis and Partial Least Square (PLS) data analysis utilizing the Smart PLS 4 Statistics application.

Table 1. Questionnaire Items

Variable	Dimension	Indicators	Question Item
Content Marketing (Andaç et al., 2016b)	Shareable	SHA 1	Content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media account are beneficial for me.
		SHA 2	I have a reason to share content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media with my friends or other subscribers.
	Easy To Understand	ETU 1	I can easily understand the information provided in the content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
		ETU 2	Content Marketing on Lazada Indonesia's social media has strong characteristics which contain photos, videos, slide shows, reels, etc. to make it easier to understand
	Incentive	INC 1	I have a desire to see and read content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
		INC 2	I have a desire to take action such as liking or commenting on content marketing posts of the Lazada Indonesia social media.

Easily Accessible	EAC 1	I can easily access content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
	EAC 2	I can easily participate in content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
Absorbing	ABS 1	I have the desire to concentrate and pay attention to absorbing information from content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
	ABS 2	I got a pleasant impression and enjoyed reading content marketing posts on Lazada Indonesia's social media.
Brand Awareness (Seo & Park, 2018)	AWR 1	I am always aware of Lazada Indonesia.
	AWR 2	I am aware of the uniqueness of Lazada Indonesia.
	AWR 3	I always recall or remember the logo of Lazada Indonesia.
Word of Mouth (Roy et al., 2019)	WOM 1	I will recommend Lazada Indonesia to others.
	WOM 2	I will say positive things about Lazada Indonesia to other people.
	WOM 3	I will encourage some people to use Lazada Indonesia.
	WOM 4	I will refer some people to Lazada Indonesia.

RESULT

A. Respondent Profiles

The profiles of the respondents are described in detail as follows: Regarding gender, the female population constitutes 61.1% while the male population accounts for 38.9%. In terms of age distribution, less than 1% of the population is under 18 years old, while 41.2% belong to the age range of 18-24 years. Additionally, 37.6% are aged between 25-34 years, and the remaining 20% are above 34 years old. The distribution of domicile is as follows: 30.6% of individuals are from Bandung, 17.6% are from Jakarta, 2.4% are from Depok, 14.1% are from Bekasi, and 18.8% are from Tangerang. Regarding occupation, 12.9% of individuals are students, 25.9% are entrepreneurs, 43.5% are full-time employers, 15.3% are employed part-time, and 2.4% belong to other categories.

B. Descriptive Statistic

This research study examines The Influence of Content Marketing Towards Word of Mouth with A Mediating Role of Brand Awareness. The study used a survey comprising 17 indicators, making use of a Likert scale with five points, with one being the "Strongly Disagree" position and five being the "Strongly Agree" position.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic

<i>Code</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Scale min</i>	<i>Scale max</i>
CM 01	3.788	2.000	5.000
CM 02	3.565	2.000	5.000
CM 03	4.024	2.000	5.000
CM 04	3.965	2.000	5.000
CM 05	3.918	2.000	5.000
CM 06	3.635	2.000	5.000
CM 07	4.047	1.000	5.000
CM 08	3.776	2.000	5.000
CM 09	3.729	2.000	5.000
CM 10	3.859	2.000	5.000
AWR 01	4.271	1.000	5.000
AWR 02	4.224	1.000	5.000
AWR 03	4.341	1.000	5.000
WOM 01	3.788	2.000	5.000
WOM 02	3.953	2.000	5.000
WOM 03	3.753	2.000	5.000
WOM 04	3.729	2.000	5.000

The table presented above offers a concise overview of descriptive data, encompassing the mean, highest, and lowest values. The code AWR 03 stands out with the highest average score of 4.34, suggesting a significant level of knowledge of Lazada Indonesia among the participants. This implies that the distinctive Lazada logo and its color scheme successfully amplify brand recognition. In contrast, the code CM 02 has the lowest mean score of 3.56. This unsatisfactory outcome indicates that the audience lacks the motivation to share Lazada Indonesia's social media content marketing posts with their friends or other subscribers. In order to address this issue, Lazada Indonesia could enhance the importance of its content by generating posts that better align with the audience's interests and requirements, potentially determined by surveys or analytics. Integrating interactive components like polls, quizzes, and challenges can enhance user engagement. In addition, providing incentives like as discount codes or the opportunity to enter a giveaway might serve as a motivation for followers to share the content.

C. Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The measuring model, also referred to as the outer model, is utilized to ascertain the relationship specification between latent variables and manifest variables. By utilizing these criteria, the study guarantees that the measurement framework reflects represents the connections between the hidden variables and their corresponding indicators, thereby establishing a strong basis for further examination of the influence of content marketing on word of mouth, mediated by brand awareness.

Convergent Validity

Based on the table below, it can be inferred that all the measured manifest variable loading factor values are above the critical value of 0.5. This indicates that all the indicators are valid and effectively contribute to explaining the constructs being generated. Furthermore, all constructs possess an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value that exceeds the critical value of 0.5.

Table 3. Outer Loading and AVE

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Indicator Variable</i>	<i>Outer Loading</i>	<i>AVE</i>	<i>Result</i>
Content Marketing	CM 01	0.890	0.640	Valid
	CM 02	0.789		Valid
	CM 03	0.787		Valid
	CM 04	0.774		Valid
	CM 05	0.822		Valid
	CM 06	0.759		Valid
	CM 07	0.753		Valid
	CM 08	0.813		Valid
	CM 09	0.790		Valid
	CM 10	0.816		Valid
Brand Awareness	AWR 01	0.857	0.750	Valid
	AWR 02	0.878		Valid
	AWR 03	0.864		Valid
Word-of-Mouth	WOM 01	0.934	0.860	Valid
	WOM 02	0.909		Valid
	WOM 03	0.954		Valid
	WOM 04	0.912		Valid

Discriminant Validity

1. Heterotrait-Monorait Ratio

The test findings indicate that the HTMT values for variable pairings are below 0.90, demonstrating the achievement of discriminant validity. This indicates that the variables exhibit a higher degree of correlation with their measurement items compared to items from other variables. Table 4 is the outcomes of this inquiry that provide proof that the measuring model is accurate. The findings of this investigation accurately measure the distinctiveness of the variables of content marketing, brand awareness, and word of

mouth, so proving the discriminant validity of these variables. This validation process guarantees the dependable usability of the constructs in subsequent investigations.

Table 4. HTMT Measurement Result

	<i>Brand Awareness</i>	<i>Content Marketing</i>	<i>Word of Mouth</i>
<i>Brand Awareness</i>			
<i>Content Marketing</i>	0.656		
<i>Word of Mouth</i>	0.662	0.848	

2. Cross Loading

The table below clearly shows that the loading factor values for each indication of construct measurement (shown by colored numbers) are much greater than the loading factor for other latent variables. Therefore, it can be inferred that all latent variables possess adequate discriminant validity.

Table 5. Cross Loading Result

	<i>Content Marketing</i>	<i>Brand Awareness</i>	<i>Word of Mouth</i>
<i>CM 01</i>	0.890	0.494	0.704
<i>CM 02</i>	0.789	0.328	0.683
<i>CM 03</i>	0.787	0.527	0.569
<i>CM 04</i>	0.774	0.513	0.617
<i>CM 05</i>	0.822	0.500	0.688
<i>CM 06</i>	0.759	0.334	0.679
<i>CM 07</i>	0.753	0.616	0.506
<i>CM 08</i>	0.813	0.478	0.620
<i>CM 09</i>	0.790	0.349	0.658
<i>CM 10</i>	0.816	0.526	0.695
<i>AWR 01</i>	0.540	0.857	0.535
<i>AWR 02</i>	0.543	0.878	0.512
<i>AWR 03</i>	0.431	0.864	0.500
<i>WOM 01</i>	0.757	0.628	0.934
<i>WOM 02</i>	0.804	0.589	0.909
<i>WOM 03</i>	0.739	0.571	0.954
<i>WOM 04</i>	0.663	0.395	0.912

Construct Reliability

Table 6. Construct Reliability Result

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Critical Value</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	<i>Result</i>
Content Marketing	0.7	0.937	0.939	Reliable
Brand Awareness	0.7	0.834	0.837	Reliable
Word of Mouth	0.7	0.946	0.951	Reliable

After examining the data in the table, it is evident that both Cronbach's alpha (CA) and Composite reliability (CR) values are above the essential critical value of 0.7. Therefore, it may be concluded that all indicators used in construction are reliable, meaning that all variables used to measure their structures have been demonstrated to be accurate, consistent, and precise.

D. Collinearity Test

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is a metric that is used to evaluate the collinearity in the circumstances of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). According to the findings of research, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was applied to determine whether or not the indicators exhibited multicollinearity. If the tolerance value is less than 0.20 and the VIF value is larger than 5, this suggests that there may be a problem with the collinearity.

Outer Model

Table 7. Collinearity Test Result (Outer Model)

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>VIF</i>
AWR 01	1.766
AWR 02	2.049
AWR 03	2.068
CM 01	4.664
CM 02	2.901
CM 03	2.790
CM 04	2.394
CM 05	2.923
CM 06	3.369
CM 07	2.318
CM 08	2.754
CM 09	2.520
CM 10	2.643
WOM 01	4.409
WOM 02	3.319
WOM 03	4.594
WOM 04	4.356

Inner Model

Table 8. Collinearity Test Result (Inner Model)

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>VIF</i>
Brand Awareness -> Word of Mouth	1.524
Content Marketing -> Brand Awareness	1.000
Content Marketing -> Word of Mouth	1.524

The tables above illustrate that all of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are below 5, suggesting no sign of any multicollinearity issue with the indicators.

E. Structural Model (Inner Model)

Evaluating the structural model or inner model involves examining the correlation value, path coefficient, and *scale of influence*, which demonstrates the ability of the structural model to make accurate predictions. As stated by Hair et al. (2019), the generally employed evaluation criteria consist of the R-squared value, the Stone-Geisser Q-statistic, and the path coefficients (B). Here are the results of the evaluation model.

Table 9. Structural Model Summary Result

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Value	Result	95% Confidence Intervals Path Coefficient		F Square	Influence
					Lower Limit	Upper Limit		
Direct Effect								
H1. Content Marketing → Brand Awareness	0.586	2.190	0.029	Significant	0.451	0.713	0.524	High Influence
H2. Content Marketing → Word of Mouth	0.691	8.726	0.000	Significant	0.569	0.833	0.947	High Influence
H3. Brand Awareness → Word of Mouth	0.191	10.278	0.000	Significant	0.008	0.347	0.072	Low Influence
Indirect Effect							Statistic Upsilon (v)	Influence
H4. Content Marketing → Brand Awareness → Word of Mouth	0.112	2.130	0.033	Significant	0.005	0.211	$(0.586)^2 \times (0.191)^2 = 0.0125$	Low Influence

H1. Content Marketing has a positive influence on Brand Awareness at Lazada Indonesia.

Hypothesis 1 states that there is a **positive** connection between content marketing and brand awareness. Since the t-value of 2.190 exceeds the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05 (5%), it means that the hypothesis is **accepted**.

The first hypothesis (H1) is **accepted** also because there is a statistically significant influence of content marketing on brand awareness, with a path coefficient of 0.586 and a p-value of 0.029 (< critical value of 0.05). Moreover, any modification in content marketing will result in an increased degree of brand awareness. Within a 95% confidence interval, the influence of content marketing on increasing brand awareness falls between the values of 0.451 and 0.713. However, content marketing has a significant influence on increasing brand awareness, as evidenced by a high structural influence (f square = 0.524). Increasing the effectiveness of content marketing is regarded as crucial because it is projected that each improvement in content marketing at Lazada Indonesia would result maximum 0.713 increase in brand awareness.

H2. Content Marketing has a positive influence on Word of Mouth at Lazada Indonesia.

Hypothesis 2 states that there is a **positive** connection between content marketing and word of mouth. Since the t-value of 8.726 exceeds the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05 (5%), it is possible to draw the conclusion that this hypothesis is **accepted**.

The second hypothesis (H2) is **accepted** also because there is a statistically significant influence of content marketing on word of mouth, with a path coefficient of 0.691 and a p-value of 0.000 (which is below the critical value of 0.05). Therefore, any modification in content marketing will result in an increased degree of word of mouth. Within a 95% confidence interval, the influence of content marketing on increasing word of mouth falls between the values of 0.569 and 0.833. However, content marketing has a significant influence on increasing brand awareness, as evidenced by a high structural influence (f square = 0.947). Increasing the effectiveness

of content marketing is regarded as crucial because it is anticipated that every improvement in content marketing at Lazada Indonesia would increase word of mouth by a maximum of 0.833.

H3. Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Word of Mouth at Lazada Indonesia.

Hypothesis 3 states that there is a **positive** connection between brand awareness and word of mouth. Since the t-value of 10.278 exceeds the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05 (5%), it is possible to draw the conclusion that this hypothesis is **accepted**.

The third hypothesis (H3) is **accepted** also because there is a statistically significant influence of brand awareness on word of mouth, with a path coefficient of 0.191 and a p-value of 0.000 (which is below the critical value of 0.05). Therefore, any increase in brand awareness will result in an increased degree of word of mouth. Within a 95% confidence interval, the influence of brand awareness on increasing word of mouth falls between the values of 0.008 and 0.347. However, brand awareness has a lower influence on increasing word of mouth, as evidenced by a low structural influence (f square = 0.072).

H4. Content Marketing has a position influence on Word of Mouth through Brand Awareness at Lazada Indonesia.

Hypothesis 4 states that there is a **positive** connection between content marketing on word of mouth through brand awareness. Since the t-value of 2.130 exceeds the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05 (5%), it can be summarized that the hypothesis is **accepted**.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) is **accepted** also because there is a statistically significant influence of content marketing on word of mouth through brand awareness, with a path coefficient of 0.112 and a p-value of 0.033 (which is below the critical value of 0.05). Therefore, any increase in content marketing will result in an increased degree of brand awareness and word of mouth. Within a 95% confidence interval, the influence of content marketing on increasing word of mouth through brand awareness falls between the values of 0.005 and 0.211. However, content marketing through brand awareness has a lower influence on increasing word of mouth, as evidenced by a low structural influence (statistic ϵ = 0.0125).

Figure II. Hypothesis Testing Result

F. Goodness of Fit

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

In statistical analysis, the coefficient of determination is a numerical value that indicates the extent to which exogenous latent factors influence the endogenous latent variables. The results of the tests are summarized in the table that is presented below:

Table 10. R Square Result

	R-square	Contribution	Other Factors
Content Marketing → Brand Awareness	0.344	34.4%	65.6%
Content Marketing, Brand Awareness → Word of Mouth	0.669	66.9%	33.1%

The table above shows the R² result. The R² is the proportion of variances that are accounted for by the structural model for endogenous variables. In the social and behavioral sciences, a value of R² equal to 0.25 is considered to indicate a minor influence, while a value of 0.50 is considered to indicate a median effect. A value of 0.75 is considered to indicate a large effect (Ringle et al., 2014). Content marketing accounts for 0.344 of the variances in brand awareness. Additionally, it is discovered that content marketing influences 34.4% of brand awareness, while the remaining 65.6% (1-R Squared) is attributed to the influence of other factors. Moreover, the proportion of variance in word of mouth that can be accounted for by both content marketing and brand awareness is 0.669. The combined influence of content marketing and brand recognition on word of mouth is 66.9%, with the remaining 33.1% attributed to other factors.

Cross-Validated Redundancy (Stone-Geisser Q²)

The table above shows that both brand awareness and word of mouth have Q² values greater than 0, indicating that they have passed the predictive relevance test effectively. The Q² result of 0.3642 implies a moderate level of predictive significance. The Q² score of 0.633 indicates a substantial and highly predictive importance in word-of-mouth communication.

Table 11. Cross-Validated Redundancy Result

	Q ² predict
Brand Awareness	0.323
Word of Mouth	0.633

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This study emphasizes the substantial influence of content marketing on brand awareness and word-of-mouth marketing at Lazada Indonesia. The findings of this investigation are described as follows. First, content marketing exerted a positive influence on the level of brand awareness. Second, content marketing exerted a significant positive influence on word of mouth. Third, brand awareness had a positive influence on word of mouth, but only to a less significant extent. Furthermore, content marketing showed a positive influence on word of mouth through brand awareness. The results highlight the significance of implementing effective content marketing strategies to establish and sustain brand awareness while encouraging positive word-of-mouth communication. The results indicate that enhancing content marketing would positively influence brand awareness and word of mouth. This is particularly crucial in the sector of e-commerce, including in the context of Lazada Indonesia. Furthermore, it indicates that it is possible to build up a positive word of mouth using content marketing on social media, which serves as a strong word-of-mouth marketing instrument.

In consideration of Lazada Indonesia's current predicaments, such as decreasing visitor quantity and trailing behind competitors in the e-commerce industry, it is essential for the company to improve its content marketing strategy. Lazada should prioritize the development of captivating and top-notch content that effectively connects with its target audience on various social media channels. By implementing this strategy, Lazada may enhance brand awareness and foster favorable word-of-mouth, therefore enticing potential customers and maintaining existing customers. Furthermore, it is essential to constantly evaluate and modify content marketing strategies to ensure their effectiveness and relevance in a dynamic market context. By allocating resources towards techniques for data analytics and consumer feedback mechanisms, Lazada Indonesia can optimize the efficiency of these initiatives, resulting in long-term growth and a stronger competitive position.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker, David. A. (1991). *Managing Brand Equity: Capitalizing on the Value of a Brand Name*. New York: Free Press.
2. Aaker, David. A. (1996). *Building Strong Brands*. New York: The Free Press.

3. Ajina, A. S. (2019). THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT IN INFLUENCING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN SAUDI BANKING INDUSTRY. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 9(3), 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.32479/irmm.8060>
4. Andaç, A., Akbıyık, F., & Karkar, A. (2016). Customer Satisfaction Factor in Digital Content Marketing: Isparta Province as an Example. *International Journal of Social Science Studies*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.11114/ijsss.v4i5.1471>
5. East, R., Hammond, K., & Lomax, W. (2008). Measuring the influence of positive and negative word of mouth on brand purchase probability. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 25(3), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2008.04.001>
6. Farjam, S., & Hongyi, X. (2015). Reviewing the Concept of Brand Equity and Evaluating Consumer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) Models. *International Journal of Management Science And Business Administration*, 1(8), 14–29. <http://researchleap.com/category/>
7. Geneulis, S. (2011). *30-Minute Social Media Marketing: Step-By-Step Techniques to Spread the Word about Your Business* by Susan Gunelius. McGraw-Hill Education.
8. Hair, J. F., Babin, B. J., Black, W. C., & Anderson, R. E. (2019). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (8th ed.). Cengage.
9. Handley, A., & Chapman, C. C. (2011). *Content Rules: How to Create Killer Blogs, Podcasts, Videos, Ebooks, Webinars (and More) That Engage Customers and Ignite Your Business*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey.
10. Keller, K. L. (2009). Building strong brands in a modern marketing communications environment. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 15(2–3), 139–155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527260902757530>
11. Odden, L. (2012). *How to Attract and Engage More Customers by Integrating SEO, Social Media, and Content Marketing*. John Wiley & Sons.
12. Pang, H. (2021). Identifying associations between mobile social media users' perceived values, attitude, satisfaction, and eWOM engagement: The moderating role of affective factors. *Telematics and Informatics*, 59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2020.101561>
13. Percy, L., & Rossiter, John. R. (1992). *A model of brand awareness and brand attitude advertising strategies*. *Psychology and Marketing* (Vol. 9). 1992 John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
14. Pulizzi, J. (2012). The rise of storytelling as the new marketing. *Publishing Research Quarterly*, 28(2), 116–123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12109-012-9264-5>
15. Pulizzi, J., & Barret, N. (2009). *Get Content Get Customers: Turn Prospects into Buyers with Content Marketing*. McGraw-Hill.
16. Swanson, S. R., & Charlene Davis, J. (2003). The relationship of differential loci with perceived quality and behavioral intentions. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 17(2), 202–219. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08876040310467943>

Cite this Article: Silvi Dwi Oktaviani, Harimukti Wandebori (2024). The Influence of Content Marketing towards Word of Mouth with a Mediating Role of Brand Awareness: Study Case at Lazada Indonesia. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(7), 4800-4811